

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE AND GREEN HRM PRACTICES ON PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEES IN IT SECTOR.

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Abstract :

An environmentally friendly environment combined with green strategies can aid in the achievement of improved environmental performance. Organisation culture is little known about the factors that could act as mediators in the relationship between green human resource management practices (GHRMP) and Employee's Performance (EP). The current study investigates the impact of green human resource management practises, and organisational culture (OC), on improved efficacy of employees in IT sector. This is accomplished through the use of structured assessment tools to collect primary data on variables, which is then processed and analysed using regression models. Primary data is collected from 140 employees of IT companies in Mumbai, Navi Mumbai and Pune cites. Purpose of selecting IT industries for the present research is because they play key role in making things' paperless'. Paperless activities are certainly useful for protection of environment. Data collected is analysed using SPSS software. Mainly correlation is applied and regression model is developed.

Key words: *Green HRM, Organisation culture, Employees Performance, IT sector*

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Introduction :

Change in traditional organisational culture to environmentally friendly organisational is need of the time. Some common examples of Green HR activities include the use of company job portals for recruitment as well as the use of telephonic, online, and video interviews, among other things. This has the potential to reduce the amount of travel required by candidates, as well as the amount of paper work. Companies can offer green rewards to employees in the form of environmentally friendly workplace and lifestyle benefits, such as carbon credit offsets, free bicycles, and pollution-free vehicles for commuting to and from work, in order to encourage employees to get involved in the green agenda as part of their compensation management. The millennial generation, particularly the knowledge and highly skilled workers, is emphasising environmental consciousness as they choose their employers, whereas many employees are not aware of their responsibility to protect the environment while at work, according to research. It

is important for highly talented and knowledgeable employees to find meaning and self-actualization in their jobs in order for them to remain committed to the companies where they work, and Green HR can assist in creating this commitment by adhering to green values and practises. Other environmentally friendly activities can include reducing the amount of paper and printed materials used in recruitment, performance appraisals, and learning and development, among others. These days, organisations with a strong commitment to the environment are able to attract the best talent. Green jobs are concerned with environmental sustainability and job opportunities that are related to the environment. Having a genuine interest and passion for business fitness is something that the green servant possesses. Employee's performance in environmental sustainability is extremely important for any organization's long-term sustainability. Employees who are committed to the environment are recruited by the Human Resources manager, and employees are rewarded for meeting environmental goals such as waste reduction or energy consumption. It is the employees' personal lives that are enriched by the company's long-term values.

Literature Review :

According to V. Udhaya Geetha (2020), green human resource management is thriving all over the world. It will have a significant impact on individuals, corporations, and the global community as a whole. In addition to teaching future generations about the importance of being kind to nature and the community, it also teaches business entities a valuable lesson about being kind to themselves. Corporate, banking, healthcare, and academic institutions that implement a well-structured green human resource management policy in tandem with the advancement of green technologies will reap the benefits in the long run. Mohammed Aboramadan (2020) GWE was used to investigate the influence of GHRM practises on green results, specifically in-role, extra-role, as well as the mediating effect of GHRM practises on green results. It was discovered, using data from Palestine's higher education market, that GHRM had a positive relationship with the aforementioned outcome variables. It was discovered that GWE played a significant mediating role in the relationships under investigation. According to the findings of the study, future research should focus on specific mechanisms that underpin the relationship between GHRM and its consequences in order to contribute to the existing body of knowledge about GHRM.

Kavin, S. M., and Dr. Ramprathap, K. (2011) discussed how policies in the areas of recruitment and selection, training and growth, and reward and compensation can improve effectiveness and contribute to an increase in the POGHRM, as well as how policies in the areas of reward and compensation can improve effectiveness and contribute to an increase in the POGHRM. In accordance with ISO140001, it has been established that the organisation has a structured environmental management framework in place, and that the organisation is also prepared to implement new green policies at any time and without restriction. Probably the most noticeable aspect is that employees are aware of GHRM and are willing to consider improvements in the interest of environmental preservation and protection. In 2016, A. Anton Arulrajah provided a concise summary of the current state of the established body of green human resource management expertise, which was followed by a section on methodologies. In the summary of green human resource management, the five most important concepts of green human resource management were

discussed in detail. Green human resource management is defined as follows: the need for green human resource management, the process model for green human resource management, the outcomes and stakeholders of green human resource management, and the success of green human resource management are all covered. Environmentally friendly human resource management encompasses a wide range of micro and macro-level aspects.

According to Deepak Bangwal (2015), the purpose of this paper is to educate readers about how Green HRM can benefit or harm employees, as well as the policies and actions of their organisations in relation to the environment. Employees acquire knowledge through various means, both at work and in their personal lives, and as a result of this knowledge acquisition, individual behaviour varies in response to the environment in which they find themselves. Green human resource management can only be implemented successfully in an organisation if it is implemented successfully throughout the organisation. Providing green human resource management practises to attract individuals to an enterprise and implementing these practises to result in improved employee attitudes and behaviours are intuitively understandable concepts. Future research could provide empirical evidence that green human resource management has a positive impact.

Research Methodology:

Information relevant to the study on "Impact of Organisational Culture and Green HRM practices on performance of employees in IT sector" is collected through a structured questionnaire. Primary data of 140 respondents is collected. Primary data consist of demographic profile of respondents and information related to organization culture, Green HRM and performance of employees. Organisation culture and Green HRM are independent variables and Performance of employees is dependent variable. In the process of analysis Karl Pearson's correlation test is applied and regression model is developed. Analysis of data is presented as follows:

Demographic factors :

Demographics		Frequency	Percent
City of work	Mumbai	51	36.4
	Navi Mumbai	37	26.4
	Pune	52	37.1
Gender	Male	68	48.6
	Female	72	51.4
Age group	Up to 25 years	24	17.1
	26 to 35 years	39	27.9
	36 to 45 years	44	31.4
	Above 45 years	33	23.6

Qualification	Graduate	28	20.0
	Postgraduate	79	56.4
	Professional	33	23.6
Work experinccc	Up to 5 years	18	12.9
	6 to 10 years	8	5.7
	11 to 15 years	27	19.3
	16 to 20 years	30	21.4
	More than 20 years	57	40.7
Level of management	Lower management	25	17.9
	Middle management	74	52.9
	Top management	41	29.3

The above table indicates that out of 140 respondents considered for this study, 51 respondents are from Mumbai, 37 from Navi Mumbai and 52 from Pune. 68 are Male and 72 Female respondents. 24 respondents are aged up to 25 years, 39 are aged between 26 to 35 years, 44 are aged between 36 to 45 years and 33 are aged above 45 years. 28 respondents are graduates, 79 are postgraduates, 33 are professionals. 18 respondents have working experience of up to 5 years, 8 have working experience of 6 to 10 years, 27 have working experience of 11 to 15 years, 30 respondents have working experience of 16 to 20 years and 57 respondents have more than 20 years of experience. 25 respondents work in lower management and 41 respondents work in top management.

Cronbach's alpha test :

To validate the scale in this study Cronbach Alpha test is applied for all 140 respondents whose responses were recorded for question related to variable Green HRM and variable Organisational Culture. The Cronbach Alpha value is 0.751 and 0.755 respectively for both the variables under consideration. It is more than the required value of 0.700. Hence the test is accepted. Conclusion is scale is reliable and accepted.

Objective 1: To study the impact of Green HRM practices on the Overall Performance of the employees in the IT sector.

Null Hypothesis H_{01} : There is no significant impact of Green HRM practices on the Overall Performance of employees in the IT sector.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{11} : There is a significant impact of Green HRM practices on the Overall Performance of employees in the IT sector.

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is calculated and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Correlations			
		Overall Performance	Green HRM
Overall Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.311**
	p-value		.000
	N	140	140
Green HRM	Pearson Correlation	.311**	1
	p-value	.000	
	N	140	140

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation : The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between Green HRM practices and Overall Performance of employee is 0.311. The calculated p-value is 0.000. This is less than 0.05. Therefore, the test is rejected. Hence Null hypothesis is rejected and Alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion : There is a significant impact of Green HRM practices on the Overall Performance of employees in the IT sector.

Finding is that there is a strong Positive relationship between the Green HRM practices and Overall Performance of employees in the IT sector. The p-value suggests that, as the Green HRM practices improves there is a certain significant increase in the Overall Performance of employees.

Objective 2: To study the impact of Organisational Culture on the Overall Performance of the employees in the IT sector.

Null Hypothesis H_{02} : There is no significant impact of Organisational Culture on the Overall Performance of employees in the IT sector.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{12} : There is a significant impact of Organisational Culture on the Overall Performance of employees in the IT sector.

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is calculated and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Correlations			
		Overall Performance	Organisation Culture
Overall Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.399**
	p-value		.000
	N	140	140
Organisation Culture	Pearson Correlation	.399**	1
	p-value	.000	
	N	140	140

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation : The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between Organisational Culture and Overall Performance of employee is 0.399. The calculated p-value is 0.000. This is less than 0.05. Therefore, the test is rejected. Hence Null hypothesis is rejected and Alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion : There is a significant impact of Organisational Culture on the Overall Performance of employees in the IT sector.

Finding is that there is a strong Positive relationship between the Organisational Culture and Overall Performance of employees in the IT sector. The p-value suggests that, as the Organisational Culture improves there is a certain significant increase in the Overall Performance of employees.

Regression Analysis:

Regression Model: (Dependent variable : Overall Performance; Independent variable: Green HRM practices, Organisational Culture)

To formulate the relationship between the independent variables Green HRM practices and Organisational Culture with dependent variable Overall Performance, Linear regression is obtained. The results are as follows:

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
1	Regression	2913.671	2	1456.835	16.808	.000 ^b
	Residual	11874.435	137	86.675		
	Total	14788.105	139			
a. Dependent Variable: Overall Performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Green HRM, Organisation Culture						

The above table indicates that the p-value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, suggesting that the Regression model is significant. Using this model, the coefficients are calculated and presented in the following table:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	31.671	5.896		5.371	.000
	Organisation Culture	.306	.074	.334	4.136	.000
	Green HRM	.237	.093	.205	2.541	.012
a. Dependent Variable: Overall Performance						

The above table indicates that all the p-value for the independent variable 'Organisational Culture' and the Constant are both 0.000 respectively. The p-value for the independent variable 'Green HRM practices' is also 0.012. All these values are less than 0.05. Hence, they are considered to be significant. Therefore, the linear equation of Regression between Overall Performance and the independent variables, 'Organisational Culture' and 'Green HRM practices' is as follows:

$$\text{Overall Performance} = 31.671 + 0.306 * \text{Organisation Culture} + 0.237 * \text{Green HRM}$$

This model is used to estimate overall performance of employees for the known values of organisation culture and Green HRM.

Findings and Recommendations :

Output of the research is that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational culture and Green HRM on performance of employees in IT sector. Employers determine the value of linking employee involvement and participation in environmental management programs to improved organizational environmental performance by focusing on waste management recycling and developing environmentally friendly products through research. Unions and employees can work together to assist employers in implementing Green Human Resource Management policies and practices that will help protect and improve their employees' health and well-being. The findings of the study reveal a broad range of initiatives that these companies can undertake to contribute to the greening of their organizations.

It is recommended that Product, process, design, and technology innovation be required by companies to develop strategies for the society that will enable a healthy, peaceful, and damage-free society with sufficient natural resources available for the human future. GHRM as an initiative may be developed into one of the best practices for long-term business growth in the future.

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